

Exploring the Effects of Acoustic Frequency on Terrain Attributes and Classifications Derived from Digital Bathymetric Models at Multiple Scales

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Abstract—In recent years, new multibeam echosounders that can simultaneously collect data at multiple frequencies have become available. However, the effects of acoustic frequency on bathymetric data have yet to be characterized, as early research on these new systems has instead focused on backscatter data. Here we explore such effects by deriving terrain attributes and classifications from bathymetric data from Head Harbour, Nova Scotia, Canada, that were collected at five different operating frequencies. The geomorphometric analyses were conducted on bathymetric surfaces generated from data collected at each operating frequency using four scales of analysis. Results show that bathymetry, its derived terrain attributes, and terrain classifications produced with them are all dependent on the acoustic frequency used to collect bathymetric data. While the observed effects on the regional bathymetry were relatively minor, local bathymetry, terrain attributes and terrain classifications were highly impacted by the frequency used when collecting data. The impacts were less important when the terrain attributes and classifications were generated using broader scales of analysis. These results raise questions about how bathymetry is measured and defined and how we should interpret the outcomes of marine geomorphometric analyses. This is particularly relevant as such analyses have become a key component of marine habitat mapping and submarine geomorphology mapping.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multibeam echosounders (MBES) remain the most effective instruments for collecting continuous, high-resolution bathymetric data in waters where light cannot penetrate. They are active remote sensors that function by transmitting acoustic waves at a given frequency and measuring the return time of the signal after reflecting off the seafloor – much like LiDAR

systems do with light. This produces a point cloud that can be used to generate a digital surface model (DSM) of the seafloor, commonly referred to as a bathymetric surface. The intensity of the return is also measured to produce backscatter data that can be used as a proxy for surficial geology. MBES typically produce sound at a single frequency, which is often less than 70 kHz for deep-water systems (deeper than 200 m) and up to 500 kHz for shallow-water systems (less than 200 m). The frequency at which a sonar operates is at the discretion of its manufacturer, and no standards exist to guide that choice. Bathymetric data collected by different systems at different frequencies are almost always considered comparable as it is assumed that all systems capture the top of the seafloor accurately regardless of frequency.

In the past few years, however, a new generation of MBES systems that can collect data using multiple frequencies simultaneously has become available [1]. Research on new opportunities provided by this technology is still in its infancy, but to date, has focused mostly on backscatter data; backscatter was shown to vary significantly with frequency as a function of the interactions between acoustic wavelength and the substrate [2,3]. This may have potential implications for how bathymetry is interpreted, but they have yet to be explored. These implications can be far-reaching as bathymetry is the primary input for marine geomorphometric analyses that have become common in disciplines like marine habitat mapping, hydrodynamic modelling, and submarine geomorphology [4].

The goal of this work was to evaluate the effects of acoustic frequency on bathymetric data, and on terrain attributes and classifications that can be derived from them at multiple scales of analysis.

II. METHODS

Acoustic data were collected from Head Harbour, Nova Scotia, Canada, in October 2021, using an R2Sonic 2026 MBES. The sonar was mounted on the M/V *Eastcom* and operated at 90, 180, 270, 360, and 450 kHz frequencies simultaneously. Positioning and motion compensations were recorded with an Applanix WaveMaster GPS and IMU, respectively. Raw soundings from each frequency were processed separately in QPS Qimera, including data cleaning, and sound velocity, motion, and tidal corrections, to produce five bathymetric surfaces at 1 m horizontal resolution (Fig. 1). The cleaned acoustic data for each frequency were also imported to QPS FMGT for backscatter processing, and five surfaces were produced, also at 1 m horizontal resolution.

Figure 1. Multibeam bathymetric data in Head Harbour, Nova Scotia, Canada, collected at a 450 kHz frequency.

The five bathymetric datasets were used to generate 15 terrain attributes: slope, easternness and northerness, maximum, minimum and mean curvatures, planform and profile curvatures, twisting curvature [5], a topographic position index [6], the relative difference from mean value [7], a vector ruggedness measure [8], a surface area to planar area ratio [9], an adjusted standard deviation metric [10], and the roughness index-elevation [11]. In addition, the datasets were used to classify the study area into seven morphometric features [12]: channels, passes, peaks, pits, planar flat areas, planar slope areas, and ridges. All terrain attributes and classifications were performed using 3x3, 9x9, 27x27, and 81x81 windows of analysis, resulting

in 325 surfaces to compare. All calculations were performed using the “MultiscaleDTM” package [10] in R v. 4.2.2. The surfaces produced were first compared in terms of their descriptive statistics (minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation, range, excess kurtosis, and skewness). Correlation matrices (Pearson’s coefficients) and difference maps were also built to explore variations in spatial distribution, and frequency distributions were compared for the terrain classifications.

III. RESULTS

A. Bathymetric data

The descriptive statistics of the five bathymetric datasets were very similar, yet all difference maps between pairs of datasets show that less than 1% of pixels had identical depth values (Table I). As expected, the closer the frequencies of two datasets, the smaller their differences. In general, DSMs were shallower, less variable, and had a narrower range of depths with increasing operating frequency. Correlations between all DSMs were very high, the lowest being 0.989 between the 90 kHz and the 360 kHz DSMs. The absolute maximum difference in depths between two DSMs ranged from 42 cm (between the 270 and 450 kHz DSMs) to 1 m (between the 90 and 360 kHz DSMs). The absolute average differences between pairs of DSMs ranged from 2 to 21 cm. The absolute differences in depths, summarized in Table I, were highly spatially correlated with backscatter. Areas with higher backscatter values usually had smaller differences.

TABLE I. STATISTICAL DISTRIBUTION OF ABSOLUTE DIFFERENCES IN DEPTH BETWEEN PAIRS OF DSMs FROM DIFFERENT FREQUENCIES

DSMs Compared	Absolute Differences (cm)					
	[0]	[0-1]	[1-2]	[2-5]	[5-10]	> 10
90-180 kHz	0.05%	1.99%	1.89%	5.49%	14.88%	75.71%
90-270 kHz	0.03%	1.18%	1.28%	4.26%	5.24%	88.01%
90-360 kHz	0.02%	0.71%	0.88%	3.87%	4.77%	89.75%
90-450 kHz	0.02%	0.71%	0.86%	3.57%	4.70%	90.14%
180-270 kHz	0.16%	6.87%	9.20%	50.68%	32.01%	1.08%
180-360 kHz	0.06%	2.48%	3.28%	19.60%	64.21%	10.38%
180-450 kHz	0.05%	2.10%	2.59%	12.57%	60.32%	22.38%
270-360 kHz	0.36%	15.33%	20.96%	54.98%	8.19%	0.17%
270-450 kHz	0.19%	8.11%	11.03%	54.73%	24.89%	1.05%
360-450 kHz	0.94%	36.46%	30.47%	29.82%	2.19%	0.12%

B. Terrain Attributes

Terrain attributes demonstrated much greater differences among frequencies than bathymetry. For example, the average of the pairwise coefficients of correlation for twisting curvature generated using a 3x3 window of analysis was 0.151 (Table II).

Slope was the least affected variable with an average correlation of 0.894 among all frequencies (3x3 window). Others at this window size ranged from 0.204 (relative deviation from mean value) to 0.655 (vector ruggedness measure). Descriptive statistics confirm the high variability of terrain attributes at different frequencies. Roughness metrics were generally higher on average at lower frequencies. This was also true for slope but only when it was computed with a 3x3 or a 9x9 window of analysis; at broader scales, the average of slope was higher at higher frequencies (270 kHz with a 27x27 window, and 360 kHz with a 81x81 window).

In general, using a broader window of analysis to generate the terrain attributes increased the correlations among the different frequencies and thus reduced the differences (Table II), yet there was no consistent linear relationship observed between frequency and correlation strength. For example, many measures of curvatures had lower average correlations at a window of 27x27 than at windows of 9x9 and 81x81.

TABLE II. RANGE OF AVERAGE PAIRWISE CORRELATIONS AMONG THE SAME TERRAIN ATTRIBUTE GENERATED FROM BATHYMETRIC DATASETS OF DIFFERENT FREQUENCY, ACROSS SCALES OF ANALYSIS

Scale	Lowest \bar{x} Correlation	Attribute	Highest \bar{x} Correlation	Attribute
3x3	0.151	Twisting Curvature	0.894	Slope
9x9	0.333	Relative Deviation from Mean Value	0.984	
27x27	0.553		0.944	Adjusted Standard Deviation
81x81	0.410	Roughness Index-Elevation	0.953	Northernness

C. Terrain Classification

As with the terrain attributes, the terrain classifications were considerably affected by the frequency of the input data. At the 3x3 scale of analysis, the morphological maps produced with 360 and 450 kHz data were the most similar, yet 53% of the study area was classified differently in the two maps. This increased to 71% between the maps produced with 90 kHz and 360 kHz. These differences among frequencies decreased when broader scales of analysis were used, ranging from 42 to 57% at 9x9, from 22 to 78% at 27x27, and between 1 and 6% at 81x81.

The differences are also reflected in the relative coverage of the different morphological features. For example, the finer-scale analysis of the 90 kHz data indicated that 30% of the study area was channels, 29% ridges, and 25% passes. When the analysis was repeated using the 450 kHz bathymetric data as input, these numbers changed respectively to 16%, 16%, and 42%. These three feature types were the most variable with changing frequency, followed by pits and peaks. The relative coverage confirms the previous observation that the variability is smaller when the analysis is performed at broader spatial scales.

IV. DISCUSSION

While the differences among bathymetric surfaces were widespread and could reach up to 1 m in places (Table 1), the high correlations among DSMs indicate that the spatial distribution of depth values remains relatively similar. This suggests that the effects of frequency on bathymetric data are primarily local, with low impact on the regional representation of the seafloor. The fact that higher frequencies produced generally shallower depths aligns with the theory behind signal penetration.

Terrain attributes were highly frequency-dependent, yet little consistency was observed in the relationships between frequencies and the statistical and spatial distributions of terrain attribute values. The results for both bathymetry and the terrain attributes raise questions about what is measured by the acoustic signal, and about how fine-scale interactions between the acoustic signal and the composition of the seafloor affect the response. This has implications for how these datasets can be used in subsequent analyses in various contexts. While additional field experiments are necessary to answer these questions, the seafloor is largely inaccessible to broad-scale and detailed ground-truthing. Additionally, it is virtually impossible to fully replicate complex field conditions in experimental tanks due to spatiotemporal variability in oceanographic conditions that may affect the interactions between the mechanical acoustic waves and the components of the transmission medium and the target. A bathymetric lidar dataset could be used as a comparison, but water conditions in this study area (*i.e.*, turbidity) are not suitable for bathymetric lidar data collection. In addition, it may be difficult to align what is measured by sound at given frequencies with what is measured by light at a given frequency.

While this work does not address the theoretical questions surrounding marine acoustic-sediment interactions, it demonstrates important effects of acoustic frequency on recorded depth values. This has implications for multi-source datasets of multiple frequencies. Artefacts are likely where datasets of differing frequency overlap, which can then influence subsequent analyses like terrain classification. We also found that the effects on terrain attributes were amplified compared to the bathymetry. Terrain attributes may vary considerably based on the frequency at which the bathymetric data were collected, however these impacts are unpredictable as no consistent patterns could be established. A similar conclusion was reached in previous work when looking at how various artefacts in digital bathymetric models impact terrain attributes [13], raising questions about whether artefacts in the data are influencing the geomorphometric analyses. The observed frequency dependence highlights the importance of critically evaluating the fitness for use of datasets. However, despite increased awareness in the community of how sensitive bathymetry can be to survey parameters and conditions, most marine research does not have the benefit of bathymetric data at multiple frequencies, which enables comparison, validation, and multiple redundancies (and therefore, reduces data uncertainty). It also remains unclear

whether generalizations can be made, as results may be dependent on the characteristics of the local seafloor.

The variability of terrain classification with acoustic frequency was higher than initially expected, but this result aligns with the observation that frequency impacts local variability more than regional variability. When the morphological features were delineated using terrain attributes that were computed over analysis distances of 3 and 9 m, they were thus more affected by the local variability of the bathymetry. The effect decreased when characterizing morphological features at greater analysis distances (*i.e.*, 27 and 81 m). This highlights the need to match the scale of analysis with the scale of local morphological features and indicates that the quantification of finer-scale morphological patterns may be highly variable and inconsistent, especially if the geomorphometric analyses capture artefacts in the bathymetric data caused by the operating frequencies, the angular dependence of seafloor detection, or platform motion.

Future work should continue looking for patterns between acoustic frequency, bathymetry, and terrain attributes – for example by quantifying variations in spatial autocorrelation. Testing multiscale terrain attributes to identify whether they can help differentiate artefacts from real fine-scale variability, and therefore capture the relevant characteristics at broader scales regardless of frequency would also be interesting. In terms of terrain classification, we should explore how combining terrain attributes with backscatter data, which are also known to vary significantly with acoustic frequency, may impact seafloor classification. Given the low correlations observed between some of the terrain attributes that were calculated at different frequencies, it may be fair to assume that they provide different information on the first few centimetres of seafloor, and they could be considered as independent variables. This may enable testing whether combinations of terrain attributes from different frequencies allows for a better discrimination of seafloor features and characteristics than single-frequency data.

V. CONCLUSION

The ability to collect multibeam bathymetric data simultaneously at different acoustic frequencies is new, and much remains to be understood about these data's characteristics and uses. Here we compared five bathymetric datasets collected between 90 and 450 kHz, and derived 15 terrain attributes and a classification of morphological features from each. This analysis was repeated at four different spatial scales of analysis. Results show that acoustic frequency alters measured bathymetry, and that the effect is amplified for all derivatives of bathymetry. Few consistent patterns between frequency, terrain attributes, and spatial scale could be established. This work is a first step in trying to understand the utility, differences, and potential pitfalls of quantitatively characterizing the morphology of the seafloor at different acoustic frequencies.

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